

PURPOSE OF INTEGRATIVE EDUCATION AND LEVELS OF INTEGRATION

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11669295>

Abstract. This thesis describes the problems of integration in the educational process of higher educational institutions, the purpose of integrative education, the concept of integrated lesson, levels of integration, types of integration and the possibilities of its application in the educational process.

Key words: education, educational process, integration, quality of education, levels of integration, types of integration, opportunities.

Introduction:

The goal of integrative education should be to provide the student with knowledge that reflects the interdependence of parts of the world as a system, to teach the child from the earliest stages of learning to describe the whole world, in which all elements are interconnected intended. Integration as an educational tool is aimed at developing the student's knowledge, updating the existing narrow specialization in education. At the same time, integration should not replace the teaching of classical subjects, it should only integrate the acquired knowledge into a single system.

The complexity of the problem is how to dynamically develop the integration from the beginning to the end of the training. If at the beginning it is recommended to learn "a little about everything", then there is a synthesis of various knowledge and skills, at the end of the training it is necessary to know "everything about a little", that is, it is a narrow specialization, but a new integrative level.

Analyzing the literature on this issue, we can form the following definition of integration: integration is a deep, consistent, multifaceted revealed leadership of subjects, academic subjects, departments and topics of academic subjects. a natural interdependence based on leadership positions. studied processes and phenomena. Therefore, it is necessary to supplement the material of one subject with the material of another, not by combining different lessons, but by combining selected parts into a whole. In addition, with any combination of materials, the idea of the subject of the lesson should remain the leading, the main one.

The very concept of an integrated lesson remains controversial. Such a lesson can be considered as a lesson that solves specific and long-term tasks and represents a new complex unit that is qualitatively different from the planned

two or topics. Therefore, neither the presence of several teachers nor the mechanical combination of teaching materials is an indicator of the level of integration. This level is determined by the range of tasks that can be performed only through integration. This is primarily a process of increasing cognitive interest and developing general educational skills and abilities.

At the 1st level of integration, the learning material is combined within a specific topic. Studying the educational material, not memorization, makes it possible to move from science education to comprehensive education when a single whole is created from different parts of the educational material.

In the 2nd stage, the conceptual and information field of various disciplines is combined for better memorization, repetition and introduction of additional material to the topic.

Stage 3 is related to comparative-generalizing learning tasks and is expressed in the development of schoolchildren's ability to compare and contrast events and objects.

At the 4th level of integration, students themselves begin to compare facts, opinions, establish connections and patterns, and apply what has been developed. learning abilities. The goal of integrated education is to teach students to see the world as a whole and to act freely in it.

Above, we noted that integration means the process of combining parts into a whole, from the Latin language "restoration", "filling", "unification". Therefore, integration is understood in different ways depending on the application:

- web integration is the integration of various parts and systems into a single web environment;
- data integration - combining data from different sources and presenting it to users in a single form;
- political integration is a process of rapprochement of political structures aimed at mutual cooperation;
- social integration is the process of establishing acceptable relations between relatively independent social objects;
- economic integration is the process of convergence and unification of enterprises, industries, regions, countries;
- ecological integration is the process of solving a set of environmental problems related to the impact of human economic activity on the natural environment.

Thus, scientists reveal a general pedagogical feature from integrativeness and show that it describes a category of general order rather than the didactic principles of systematicity and sequence.

In many scientific works, the process of integrating the field of education is an important process, because the educational goal in the training of specialists in the field of education is the state order, that is, the training of knowledgeable engineers with a higher education and a broad outlook. will be related to the idea.

From the pedagogical point of view, such integration is the systematic organization of the same type of components and content elements, teaching methodology, within the framework of educational processes that lead to self-development of students.

In the analysis of the above literature, in today's scientific researches and studies, in pedagogical literature, we saw that our scientists expressed different opinions about the meaning and essence of "integration". In our opinion, integration consists in ensuring and rounding up the correct establishment of interdependencies and relationships between types of education, inter-subjects and inter-themes.

Conclusion:

In our opinion, integration is an important concept that affects the quality of the educational process and serves to deepen and develop students' knowledge by ensuring a certain sequence and consistency of a certain stage, subject or topic of education

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